

Historical-demographic processes in the world in the era of globalization and its impact on urbanization.

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Abstract: This article analyzes the rapid development of the world's pace of life in the process of globalization, historical-demographic processes, positive aspects of globalization, and the fact that there are a number of serious problems, its impact on urbanization, and the fact that there are different views in science about the positive and negative aspects of globalization.

Today, humanity is living in a time of complex conflict, which is changing rapidly and is completely different from the times experienced in the past history.

Nowadays, it is becoming common for people in other regions of the world to be immediately informed about the events happening on the other side of the earth. Thanks to the Internet connection, the news happening in the world is received anywhere on our mother planet.

This period is called by experts the age of high technologies, general information or ideas. But in science and practice, this idea has taken a firm place with the term globalization. As noted by Professor N. Joraev, the term globalism is becoming more and more important in the next hundred years. The concept of "global" from the point of view of the dictionary meaning means "general" from the French language, and "globe-earth" in Latin. So, the concept of globalism, in both senses, includes "planetary", "all-planetary", "all-human", "worldly" problems, issues of "all-planetary" importance and perspectives of global development, which are directly related to the life and destiny of mankind. takes [1:408-409]. Globalization means, first of all, an incomparable acceleration of the pace of life" [2:111] So, the essence of the globalization process is the excessive expansion and complexity of communication and interdependence between people and countries. [3:6].

Thus, the rapid development of the pace of life on the world scale showed that along with the positive aspects of globalization, it also has a number of serious problems [4:1492-1495]. It is accepted to call a certain part of them "global problems of the present time" in science. There are different views in science about the positive and negative aspects of globalization.

The positive aspects of globalization accelerate the convergence of the national and cultural life and economy of peoples and states, create favorable opportunities for their development[5:135-138].

In a broad sense, economic interdependence, globalization of information, and interdependence from the point of view of security are some of the characteristics of the globalization of today's world.

Logan and Moloch, the world's leading experts in this field, divide cities that have emerged as a result of international economic influence on urbanization processes into five types. City Headquarters Apartments, Innovation Centers, Modular Production Centers, World Loading and Unloading Points, Retirement City.

According to experts, "Globalization" in a broader sense is the growth of national and regional problems into global problems and the formation of a new economic and economic natural and biological environment.

Globalization processes in the world, as in other areas, have positive and negative effects on the appearance of world cities and lifestyle[6:1-6]. Although various proposals and recommendations are given by experts to find solutions to the problems caused by globalization, fundamental proposals in this area are still missing.

Economic globalization creates an opportunity for the complexity of the urban system, for it to have a new place in the development of society. This process has both positive and negative effects on cities. Large cities-due to globalization[7:121-123] megacities are taking the position of global cities. "These megacities make up the main share of the gross domestic product of their countries. In particular, about 30 megacities of the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development [8:96-100] (OECD) account for 10-50% of the GDP of those countries[13].

Among them, Copenhagen leads with 49.6% of Denmark's GDP. The cities of Dublin, Brussels, and Budapest account for 42-47% of the GDP of their countries. Vienna, London, Paris, Stockholm and Tokyo share 28-34% of the state GDP of the national GDP"[12]

Cities that are becoming global are being called by different names. In particular, J. Gottmann uses the terms "Megapolis", P. Hall, J. Friedman "World city", S. Logan and G. Molotch "headquarters", M. Kostels "Information city", S. Sastsen "global city" and terms are becoming popular today[14:145].

• In the center of the globalization process is the acceleration of information and information technologies, the development of social-political and economic structures on a global scale, and the international importance of the financial market. Saskia Sastsen in her book "Global City: New York, London, Tokyo" describes global cities as the center that produces political solutions for the global economy, the main point where financial and specialized service firms that influence the economy are located[15]. The following characteristics of the global city can be distinguished from the opinions of the above researchers:

- Size of the city (population);
- International role as a trade and financial center; the development of various service areas;
- Importance as an information center, development of information functions;
- It plays an important role as a national and world center, the location of government organizations;
- Existence of international organizations and importance of international functions, location of headquarters of multinational corporations, offices of international companies;
- Its role as a national and world trade center;
- The fact that it is a highly developed activity center;
- Leadership as a center of culture and art;
- The role of major international transport connections;
- Growth of social and economic disparities[16].

The analysis shows that modern urbanization processes are progressing in an integral connection with globalization processes.

With the incomparable influence of globalization[9:128-131], the processes of urbanization are accelerating, small towns are relatively expanding, and big cities are getting bigger. As a result, during the 20th century, it was observed that the pace of the urban situation on the world scale accelerated.

The rapid development of the economy, the revolutionary penetration of modern technology into the production sector, the rapid development of transport and communication, the wide spread of population migration at the international level, and other factors accelerate the urbanistic processes and sharply differentiate the urban lifestyle from the rural life. brought

Urbanization [11:73-76] is a historical process that represents the way of life associated with the development of cities, and the amount of cities in the accumulation of population within the territory and regions, and the determination of their size and size indicates the place of cities in various aspects of community life [12:26-28].

The development of cities is characterized by the development of social and economic spheres of the society and the improvement of the standard of living and lifestyle of the population.

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